

Informed Health Choices Project: Teaching people to think critically about health claims, comparisons and choices

UNIVERSITY OF RWANDA- CHOICE PROJECT

A list of Students' who were approved to participate in the choice trial

School name:.....

School code:.....

District:.....

Sector.....

NO	First Name	Other name	Age	Gender	Class	Accepted to participate in students' network	Signed assent
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CHOICE PROJECT

Informed Health Choices Project: Teaching people to think critically about health claims, comparisons and choices

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Research team member

Teacher responsible

Head teacher of the school

Name:

Name:

Name:

Signature

Signature:

Signature: